

Southern California CSU DNP Consortium

California State University, Fullerton
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REDUCING PATIENT TO STAFF ASSAULTS ON THE MEDICAL SURGICAL WARDS

A DOCTORAL PROJECT

Submitted in Partial Fulfillment of the Requirements

For the degree of

DOCTOR OF NURSING PRACTICE

By

Artiyanee Ann Boonjaluksa

Doctoral Project Committee Approval:

Beverly Quaye, EdD, PHN, NEA-BC, FACHE, Team Leadet
Laura Sarff, DNP, RN, MBA, CPHQ, NEA-BC, Team Member

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Author Note

Artiyanee Ann Boonjaluksa- <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-9447-8608>

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ABSTRACT

Background: Workplace violence (WPV) is a serious and growing problem. Nurses have the highest risk for assault due to having more direct patient contact than any other healthcare (HC) workers (Ferri et al., 2016). In 2019, the Senate passed a bill requiring HC employers to implement a WPV prevention plan.

Purpose: Implement a WPV prevention plan called the Golden Hand (GH) Tool Kit to reduce assaults on medical-surgical (MS) wards to include:

- Staff education
- Violence prediction assessment
- Additional security for Behavioral Response Team (BRT)
- Safety huddles

Methods: Analyze the pre- and post-implementation staff survey results and the numbers of assaults from the Safety Intelligence (SI) system to evaluate the project's effectiveness.

Results: Based on survey data n=267, staff were in favor of the project and found it beneficial. Reports from SI showed assaults decreased and the time between assaults increased on Ward A; however, no initial improvement on Ward B. In December, a process change was made on Ward B to increase the use of the violence prediction tool to all patients daily. During the 11 weeks of study that followed, there were no patient-to-staff assaults reported on Ward A or B. The project has shown the GH system has an overall positive effect on the reduction of WPV and has even more potential for success with more time and continuous improvements.

Conclusion: The GH Tool Kit demonstrates an effective outcome in reducing patient-to-staff assaults in the MS setting in its post-implementation measurement.

Keywords: assaults, workplace violence, prediction

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Background

In Massachusetts, a patient nearly tears off a nurse's ear and attempts to gouge out her eye while assisting a transfer from one restraint system to another (Burrell, 2016). In Utah, a nurse gets punched in the face when she tries to prevent a mentally ill patient from leaving the hospital (Edwards, 2018). In Los Angeles, a registered nurse (RN) gets strangled by a patient with her stethoscope when she attempts to help another nurse during an assault. She survived the attack but was out of work for six weeks and developed post-traumatic stress disorder (Skerrett, 2015). Workplace violence is a serious and growing problem that needs to be addressed.

Workplace violence is an act of any physical assault, harassment, intimidation, threatening behavior, or verbal abuse occurring in the work setting (Wei et al., 2016). Patient violence against nurses is growing globally and is most prevalent in the mental health care setting (Lantta et al., 2016). In 2000, a study showed that 82% of nurses in the US reported having been assaulted at least once in their careers (Speroni et al., 2014, as cited in Watson et al., 2020). Areas of violent incidents outside of mental health care frequently include emergency departments and nursing homes (Edward et al., 2014). According to Ferri et al. (2016), nurses and nursing attendants have the highest risk of being assaulted compared to other healthcare personnel because they have more direct contact with patients. Additionally, as a result of the patient-to-nurse assaults, they often experience a form of post-traumatic stress disorder with a significant effect on their physical and mental well-being (Martinez, 2016).

Most studies on workplace violence in the hospital pertain to incidents in the psychiatric wards or emergency rooms. MS areas have often been excluded in the literature; however, a cross-sectional study concluded that medical-surgical nurses had more psychological distress and sleep disturbance after patient aggression than nurses in psychiatric or emergency settings

(Pekurinen et al., 2017). The findings could be due to deficits in skill proficiency, a lack of training, or inadequate staffing to prevent aggressive and violent patient behavior. If the patient-to-nurse assaults continue to grow without effective interventions to manage patient behavior, we will encounter an increasing shortage of frontline nurses due to fear and safety concerns. The workforce is already experiencing higher numbers of nurses on injury leave and those who chose not to return to the workplace due to distress and anxiety post-assault (Casey, 2019; Wei et al., 2016).

Problem Statement

Workplace violence (WPV) is on the rise. Frontline nurses, who spend more time interacting with patients and family members than any other acute care personnel, are getting assaulted and injured. Historically, most quality improvement (QI) projects have been conducted in emergency and psychiatric departments, with few in medical-surgical areas. In a 600-bed acute care hospital in the heart of Los Angeles, there were 14 reported incidents of patient to staff assaults from October to December, 2019, on two medical-surgical wards (combined occupancy of 56 beds), compared to only four incidents on six psychiatric wards (combined occupancy of 60 beds). The medical-surgical incidents are exponential compared to the psychiatric wards' incidences. They require timely analysis and interventions to prevent and reduce patient violence and ensure an environment of safety.

Furthermore, guidelines from regulatory agencies require that employers address WPV. The Occupational Safety and Health Administration (OSHA) has been enforcing the employer's obligation to address WPV under the General Duty Clause of 1970 (United States Department of Labor, 2002). The Joint Commission regulates WPV under the Environment of Care standards EC.02.01.01 and Leadership EC. 03.01.01 (Sentinel Event Alert, 2018). The US Senate recently

approved a bill called the "Workplace Violence Prevention for Healthcare and Social Service Workers Act" (GovTrack, 2020), which requires employers to develop and implement a detailed WPV prevention plan. Therefore, it is apropos to create and implement a QI project to adhere to regulatory requirements and protect the staff's well-being.

Purpose Statement

The purpose of the project was to implement a WPV prevention program called the Golden Hand Tool Kit to reduce the number of physical assaults on frontline staff. This project aimed to reduce the number of physical assaults on nursing staff on two medical-surgical wards in a large acute care hospital in Los Angeles. The Golden Hand Tool Kit is comprised of four interventions: (a) staff education, (b) use of a violence risk assessment tool, (c) inclusion of security personnel as part of a response team to help manage violent patients, and (d) daily safety huddles.

Supporting Framework

Frameworks are used to establish a foundation and provide guidelines for implementing evidence-based practice or performance improvements at the Doctor of Nursing Practice (DNP) level (Bonnell & Smith, 2017). The most suitable framework for this project was the Institute for Healthcare Improvement's (IHI) Rapid Improvement Model. The hospital had successfully utilized the Rapid Improvement Model for several QI projects and was familiar with its steps and simplicity. The current IHI Model integrated two earlier improvement models: The Model for Improvement, developed by the Associates in Process Improvement (Langley et al., 2009), and the Plan-Do-Study-Act (PDSA) tool from 1993 (Taylor et al., 2014). The IHI model has two parts: (a) Part 1- three fundamental questions were asked;

1. What are we trying to accomplish?

2. How will we know the change is an improvement?
3. What change can we make that will result in improvement?

And, (b) Part 2 - the PDSA cycles (Figures 1-3) structure the project steps (Powell et al.,2009).

Figure 1

IHI Part 2- PDSA Cycle 1

Figure 2

IHI Part 2- PDSA Cycle 2

Figure 3

IHI Part 2- PDSA Cycle 3

Institute for Healthcare Improvement - Model for Improvement: The Three Questions

What Are We Trying to Accomplish?

This program's initial implementation was not successful due to a temporary shift in the organization's focus. The project's goal changed to evaluate and modify the use of the GH toolkit for nurses to reduce the number of patient-to-nurse assaults in two MS wards. A tool kit is a resource with quality indicators used to track and guide an improvement project (Agency for Healthcare Research and Quality, 2017). Ward A is a 32-bed medical-surgical ward with a patient-to-nurse ratio of 5:1. Ward B is a 24-bed medical-surgical ward with a patient-to-nurse ratio of 5:1. Both Wards A and B staffing plans included a team leader, registered nurses, a ward-support clerk, and an average of three nursing attendants for the direct care ratios of 5:1. Ward A cares for patients with medical-surgical diagnoses compared to Ward B that cares for patients with medical-surgical diagnoses of behavioral issues. These issues include patients with mental health comorbidities, a history of violence, and an involuntary psychiatric hold to protect them from self-harm or harm to others.

How Will You Know the Change is an Improvement?

Data was collected on staff assaults through the Safety Intelligence© platform, an electronic system that tracks adverse events by ward. Data on staff assaults were aggregated monthly and displayed on a run chart to identify reductions in staff assaults as the outcome measure. Also, the process measures included the daily percentage of Brøset Violence Checklist (BVC) tool completion and the completion of every shift unit huddle captured on a run chart.

What Change Can We Make that will Result in Improvement?

The first intervention was to form the project team including the Clinical Nursing Director, nurse supervisor, frontline nurses, QI nurse, and BRT team. A study by Mu et al.

(2018) showed that projects comprised of frontline staff and management had a positive effect and higher innovative outcomes.

The second intervention was called the Golden Hand, which used the BVC tool to assess violent behavior. The BVC originated from empirical work by Linaker and Busch-Iversen from Norway in 1995 (Likaker & Busch-Iversen, 1995; Woods & Almvik, 2002). The study showed that there were six common behaviors that patients exhibited before the violent incident including confusion, irritability, boisterousness, physical threats, verbal threats, and attacking objects (Woods & Almvik, 2002). Studies support that the BVC was a valid and reliable tool (Andersen & Jenson, 2019; Moursel et al., 2019; Partridge & Affleck, 2018). The six common behaviors were used to screen patient behaviors on admission, every 24 hours, and with any change in condition. A patient determined to be at high risk for violence was identified with a Golden Hand symbol placed on the patient's room door and over their bed. A Golden Hand patient wrist band was applied for healthcare personnel to identify potentially violent behavior. There was also a Golden Hand protocol with identified safety steps that need to be implemented, such as maintaining minimum leg distance and ensuring that two staff were present when administering physical care.

The third intervention was the use of a behavioral response team (BRT). Studies supported that implementing a BRT helps stabilize a behavioral crisis (Afriyie-Boateng et al., 2019; Zicko et al., 2017). The ward could activate a Code Gold for patients who are escalating or are dangerous toward themselves or others. The BRT consists of three skilled nursing and support staff (one registered nurse and two nursing attendants) and two security staff in uniform. The team was trained in non-violence prevention skills and the management of aggressive behaviors. The training was done by the Crisis Prevention Institute (CPI) instructors and

endorsed by the Joint Commission (Daum, 2019; Vittone,2019). According to Morphet et al. (2018), studies showed that just the aggression management team's presence, such as the BRT, was often enough to de-escalate the situation.

IHI Model for Improvement: Plan, Do, Study, Act

The second part of the IHI Model was to use PDSA cycles to manage and make a planned change and avoid disruption, making it a practical framework to use in a patient care setting. The PDSA cycle, also known as the Deming cycle, was created by Dr. William Edwards Deming, a management and efficiency expert in the 1950s. Deming referred to PDSA as the "Shewhart Cycle" because of his mentor's influence, Walter Shewhart (Moen, n.d.). In this project, the PDSA cycle was used to improve the implementation of the Golden Hand Tool Kit's specific components, as described in Figures 1 through 3.

To achieve change progression within the project, the improvement team determined if they would adapt, adopt, or abandon the tested change under the Act phase. "Adapt" meant that the test would be adjusted to try to get a better result. To "adopt" meant that the change was successful and can be replicated and tested in other wards. Moreover, to "abandon" meant that the test was unsuccessful and that the intervention was terminated (Jessee, 2019). The plan was for team members to debrief the test of change and re-evaluate the next steps. The PDSA cycles were essential to ensure that the project was effective and sustainable before spreading it to other potential patient care areas. PDSA cycles anticipated are displayed in Figures 1-3. PDSA cycles' goal was to conduct interative tests of change to determine the best methods for sustained improvement.

Review of Literature

Search Strategies

A comprehensive literature review was conducted for this QI project using CINAHL, PubMed, Google Scholar, and One Search (Tables 1,2,3). Searches were conducted for evidence related to reducing workplace violence, predicting violent or aggressive behaviors, security personnel to reduce violence, and violence against nurses. MeSH and key terms were used and included “aggression,” “security personnel,” “workplace,” “acute-care hospital,” “safety huddles,” and “healthcare.” The search limits were peer-review articles, from 2015-2020, in English, human, and adult. The inclusion criteria included psychiatric inpatient setting, emergency department, and medical-surgical ward. Although the project's focus was on medical-surgical wards, there were limited peer-reviewed articles found pertaining only to workplace violence in the medical-surgical ward; therefore, the search was expanded to include psychiatric and emergency settings. The exclusion criteria were repetitive articles, non-acute care settings, nursing homes, jail, and employee-to-employee assaults. Of the articles selected and reviewed, those pertaining to assaults against nursing students, physicians, or other non-nursing staff were excluded because this project's focus was on nurses. Articles were screened for compatibility and similarity to the healthcare practice in the United States.

The purpose of this project was to reduce the patient-to-staff assaults in the medical-surgical wards. According to Polit and Beck (2017), a thorough literature review is a foundation for new ideas. A literature search was conducted in the following areas: violence in healthcare settings, reducing nurse assaults, security personnel to manage violent patients, and assessment tools for violent behaviors.

Table 1*Violent Patients*

Terms	Limiters	Articles Retrieved	Articles Excluded	Articles Reviewed	Articles used
“Violent patients” and “hospitals”	Peer-Reviewed, English language, Published date 2015-2020	PubMed:37	43	7	4
“Aggressive patient” and “nurse” and “United States”	Peer-Reviewed, English language, Published date 2015-2020	PubMed:37 CINAHL:18 OS:52	106	19	9
“Type II violence” and “hospitals “ and “nurse” and “United States”	Peer-Reviewed, English language, Published date 2015-2020	OS:142	127	15	8

Note: Articles excluded were based on titles or abstract and significance to the project topic. CINAHL = Cumulative Index Nursing and Allied Health Literature (CINALH); GS = Google Scholar; OS = One Search (includes Science direct, OVID, SAGE, and EBSCO)

Table 2*Brøset Violence Checklist*

Terms	Limiters	Articles Retrieved	Articles Excluded	Articles Reviewed	Articles used
Brøset Violence Checklist	Peer-Reviewed, English language, Published date 2015-2020	PubMed:54 CINAHL:9 GS:9 OS:43	102	13	8

Note: Articles excluded were based on titles or abstracts and significance to the project topic. CINAHL = Cumulative Index Nursing and Allied Health Literature (CINALH); GS = Google Scholar; OS = One Search (includes Science direct, OVID, SAGE, and EBSCO)

Table 3*Safety Huddles*

Terms	Limiters	Articles Retrieved	Articles Excluded	Articles Reviewed	Articles used
“Safety Huddles” and “hospitals”	Peer-Reviewed, English language, Published date 2015-2020	PubMed: 3 CINAHL:14 OS:1173	1085	34	5

Note: Articles excluded were based on titles or abstracts and significance to the project topic. CINAHL = Cumulative Index Nursing and Allied Health Literature (CINALH); GS = Google Scholar; OS = One Search (includes Science direct, OVID, SAGE, and EBSCO)

Workplace Violence

Workplace violence (WPV) is an act of any physical assault, harassment, intimidation, threatening behavior, or verbal abuse occurring in the work setting (Wei et al., 2016). Patient violence against nurses is one type of violence that is a growing concern throughout the world, especially in mental health care (Lantta et al., 2016). Numerous studies showed that nurses in psychiatric and emergency rooms are at a higher risk of being assaulted by the patient (Gillespie et al., 2014; Larson et al., 2019; Ridenour et al., 2017). However, a study by Pekurinen et al. (2017) argued that even though MS nurses may have a lower risk of exposure to patient assaults, the impact of the violence on non-psychiatric and non-emergency nurses is more severe due to their lack of experience in behavioral intervention skills.

Violence in the workplace has been shown to impact the victims physically, mentally, and emotionally. A study by Graham (2017) showed that nurses who experience violent physical assault in the workplace often develop post-traumatic stress disorder, impacting their overall mental and physical well-being. Nurses who experienced WPV have increased burnout rates, calling off sick, and job dissatisfaction with decreased work productivity (Phillips, 2016).

Other research by Speroni et al. (2014) found that nurses were so traumatized by the violence at their workplace that 63.3% considered leaving the hospital, and 8.8% considered leaving the nursing profession. A cross-sectional study done by Pekurinen et al. (2017) found that MS nurses suffered more from mental distress and sleep disturbance than the nurses in the psychiatric or emergency setting after exposure to violence.

WPV impacts the employer as well. The traumatic events can lead to workers' absenteeism, heightened fear, reduced morale, and increased employee turnover. Employers can face an increase in health insurance premiums or other monetary losses (Fasanya & Dada, 2016), but most profoundly, how the disruption negatively impacts the quality of care provided to patients (Rouvinen, 2019).

Violence Prediction

Most workplace violence studies have found that most nurses are highly vulnerable when caring for patients with mental illness, behavioral problems, or substance abuse use disorder (Dawson et al., 2017; Gillespie et al., 2017; Speroni et al., 2014). Numerous studies tried to determine the common characteristics of violent offenders. Three research studies, done in the United States, concluded that the perpetrators were more often males, with confusing behavior such as dementia or delirium, substance intoxication, or decompensated mental illness (Philips, 2016; Sarver et al., 2019; Speroni et al., 2014). Other studies argued that patient-related factors such as behaviors and psychopathology should not be taken out of context. We also need to consider those interpersonal variables such as patient-to-patient and patient-to-staff interactions that can also contribute to violent behavior (Philips, 2016; Szabo et al., 2015).

In looking at risk factors that contributed to workplace violence, studies found that perpetrator, worker, situational, and environmental factors are correlated to the event (Arnetz et

al., 2018). Meta-analysis studies were conducted to assess the effect of gender factors in relation to assault events. Findings showed that a significantly higher proportion of female nurses than male nurses got verbally assaulted, whereas male nurses were more likely to be victims of physical assaults (Edward et al., 2016). A retrospective study of 10,970 workers using the "Aggression Reporting Form" showed that a large portion of the assaulted workers were female (77.5%). The study also concluded that aggressive non-verbal acts generally occurred when nurses assisted or cared for patients (Viottini et al., 2020).

Violence Against Nurses

To accurately assess the issue of WPV, researchers need to be able to obtain accurate data. Studies show, however, that nursing is under-reporting workplace violence. According to the Joint Commission, only 20% of disruptive and violent behavioral incidents are reported (Brous, 2018). The reasons for under-reporting assaults include the feeling that "it's part of the job" (Blando et al., 2015; Speroni et al., 2014). Another is the reluctance to report because they are new to the position and fear that it may compromise how they are seen by management (Graham, 2017; Philips, 2016; Ridenour et al., 2015). Others believed it was pointless to report because nothing would get done anyway (Brando, 2015; Graham, 2017; Kvas & Seljak, 2014).

Interventions to Reduce Assaults

Education

Educating nurses on managing aggressive and violent patients is essential due to the increasing assault incidents in the workplace. Nurses in non-psychiatric settings may be less prepared due to their lack of training in handling patient's aggressive behaviors and de-escalation techniques (Casey, 2019; Pekurinen et al., 2017). Education has been known to improve de-escalation skills and techniques, and build confidence for nurses to effectively manage

aggressive behavior (Kvas & Seljack, 2014). Studies showed interventions improve staff education and confidence that frequently contribute to decreased violent incidents (Casey, 2019; Kynoch et al., 2011; Tölli et al., 2017). A study by Samuels et al. (2018) also supports that educating and training the staff will empower them to recognize risks that in turn reduce assaultive incidents.

Screening

Evidence supports screening and predicting aggressive patient behaviors are interventions that help reduce WPV. A retrospective study in 2012 looked at the use of the Risk of Harm to Others Clinical Assessment Protocol (RHO CAP) to predict inpatient physical aggression (Neufeld et al., 2014). An observational study by Jackson et al. (2014) utilized a Violence Assessment (VAT) to observe violent behavior cues. A retrospective study looked at two hundred and twenty-two patients using the Brøset Violence Chart (BVC) as a predictive tool to determine if the patient will become violent. The study identified the BVC to be a valuable tool (Sarver et al., 2019). Similar studies on the effectiveness of the BVC were also done using the literature search method (Andersen & Jenson, 2019; Szabo et al., 2015). Both studies also concluded that BVC was one of the most effective assessments for violence screening. All these studies were conducted in a psychiatric facility. There were no US studies on BVC utilization in the medical-surgical setting.

Security Support

Two security personnel were added to the behavioral response team (BRT) each shift to help manage violent patients. Studies showed that a security guard's presence effectively decrease violence incidents (Lenaghan et al., 2018; Ramacciati et al., 2016). Studies also showed unexpected benefits to including security personnel as part of the behavioral response team

assisting with restraints and observation, participating in interdisciplinary workplace violence prevention and management training (Gillespie et al., 2014; Kelley, 2014).

Huddles

Daily huddles were implemented to communicate safety issues related to patient care and unit-level operational needs. The safety huddle included leadership, the nursing team, providers, support staff, and BRT members. Studies showed that huddles improve communication and heightened awareness of safety concerns (Melto et al., 2017; Pimentel et al., 2021). However, the key to ensuring effective safety huddles is to get the buy-in from the multidisciplinary team and a strong commitment from leadership (Glymph et al., 2015; Montague et al., 2019).

Methods

Design

The project's purpose was to implement a WPV prevention program called the Golden Hand Tool Kit to reduce the number of physical assaults on nursing staff in two medical-surgical wards located in a large acute care hospital in Los Angeles. A Golden Hand Tool Kit was selected based on the success of a current assault reduction program in the emergency department and was modified for the medical-surgical wards. Evidence from the review of literature of the tool validated successful outcomes. The tool kit included training, violence prediction tool, signage, patient's wristband, BRT participation, and safety huddles. The project was implemented on February 16, 2020; however, the implementation was ineffective during the COVID 19 pandemic. Within 30 days, the hospital's priority had a drastic shift due to the COVID-19 virus, diverting resources, and internal disaster response needed to accommodate LA County patients.

Before the emergent crisis, the team completed four 60-minute training classes scheduled over two weeks, two on days, one on evenings, and one on the night shift. The team utilized the train the trainer's method (Marks et al., 2013; Nakamura et al., 2014). The selected trainees then trained the nursing staff, who were not able to attend the class. Before the hospital reached the emergency crisis stage that halted the project, Ward A and B and the BRT staff were fully trained on the GH project. In September 2020, when the project was approved to resume, the staff was refreshed on the GH hand protocols. The project was re-implemented with heightened supervision and management of its processes.

Setting and Participants

The QI project took place at LAC-USC, where two acute care wards participated in this pilot project. One was a 32-bed medical-surgical ward whose patient population includes multi-system acute and chronic medical and surgical care patients. The other was a 24-bed medical-surgical behavioral ward with mental health comorbidities and behavioral issues. The team selected two wards for the pilot due to their high rate of patient-to-nurse assaults.

The population for this project included all nurses employed in the two medical-surgical wards in Fall 2020. Each unit has approximately 65 nursing staff with various roles, i.e., nurse manager, supervisors, registered nurses, licensed vocational nurses, nursing attendants, clerical staff, plus 25 behavioral response team members, i.e., nursing attendants and security staff.

The Institution Review Board (IRB) application was submitted to the CSUF Cayuse Institutional Review Board (IRB) and approved as exempt from human subjects. A pre-survey was given to the participants to assess their knowledge and attitude before re-implementation. Completion of the survey implied their consent in this QI project.

Procedure

An ad hoc team was created for the initial project and remained active and committed to reducing patient-to-staff assaults in the medical-surgical areas. Baseline data for the number of assaults was extracted from the University Health System Consortium (UHC) Safety Intelligence (SI) event reporting database from January 1, 2019, to December 31, 2019. The clinical nursing director (CND) conducted a literature search using CINAHL, peer-reviewed articles and published within the last five years for studies on interventions to reduce workplace violence. Based on the literature review, the team agreed upon implementing training for the nursing staff, using the BVC, involving the behavioral response team in the medical-surgical ward, and

conducting a post-assault debrief. The IHI Model for Improvement was used as the framework to help guide the project.

Two educators from the hospital's Education and Consulting Services (EDCOS) developed the training and training materials. Both were crisis intervention trainers certified by the CPI. The educators and the CND determined the training curriculum and the number of training sessions. In a follow-up meeting held on July 2, 2020, the QI team decided that it was necessary to re-evaluate the project by administering a survey to the nursing staff on the two medical-surgical wards before re-implementation.

A project survey was created by the educators based on the training objectives. The survey included the following eight statements and used a Likert response (5= strongly agree, 4=agree, 3=neutral, 2=disagree, and 1=strongly disagree). Project leaders handed the paper survey to each staff member before the start of the project and at the conclusion of the project.

Project Survey

1. I am able to identify potentially assaultive/violent patients to help prevent staff assaults in my work area.
2. The current methods, policies, and procedures we have in place help prevent staff from assaults in my work area.
3. I depend on the patients' current behaviors to determine whether a patient has the potential for violence.
4. I depend on the patients' social and medical history to determine whether a patient has the potential for violence.
5. How many times has a patient assaulted you in the last three months?

6. The Golden Hand pilot has made me more aware of the potential assaultive patients on my unit.
7. The GH documentation is easy to complete.
8. I feel safer with the GH implementation.

In the literature search, several violent predictive tools were observed, such as the Short-term Assessment of Risk and Treatability (START), Dynamic Appraisal of Situation Aggression-Inpatient Version (DASA-IV), and Violence Risk Screening -10V (RISK-10). The BVC was chosen, however, based on its compatibility with the CPI Crisis Model. Studies support that the BVC was a valid and reliable tool (Moursel et al., 2019; Partridge & Affleck, 2018). The Joint Commission also referenced the BVC as a valid tool to use (Daum, 2019). This tool was also reviewed by the hospital's Safety Office and deemed to meet OSHA standards for screening patients. The nurses were then trained on using the BVC tool and provided sample forms to practice their assessment during class. The BVC consisted of six behaviors: confused, irritable, boisterous, physically threatening, verbally threatening, and attacking objects. The nurse screened the patients upon admission, a minimum of every 24 hours, and with a change in condition. Each behavior was rated 0 or 1; 0 meant that the act as not demonstrated, and 1 means that it was shown. The total sum of 0 indicated that the violence risk was small, and no action was needed. A sum of 1-2 indicated moderate risk and to activate the GH protocol. A sum of 3-6 meant that the patient was at high risk and to activate the GH and consider calling a Code Gold, which was calling in the BRT's assistance. If any of the behaviors under moderate or high risk included physical or verbal threats, the staff would activate a Code Gold.

The GH Protocol required the placement of the GH sign outside of the patient's room in a visible location and applied the GH wristband to identify the patient. Nurses are required to do a

sharps check on admission and all returns to the ward. When observing the patient, the staff were to maintain a minimum leg length distance. Furthermore, two staff are to be present when providing physical care to the patient. The nurse would inform the patient that they were on assaultive precautions and advise them on reassessment criteria.

If the patient demonstrated a physical or verbal threat, the staff would call a Code Gold to alert the BRT. The BRT's function is to de-escalate the agitated patient based on CPI interventions verbally. The BRT would use physical restraints as a last resort for the safety of the patient or others. The BRT security guards would round every shift on identified GH patients to remain informed of any changes in patient's conditions and offer support and reinforcement to the patient care staff.

Lastly, each unit conducted daily huddles. Huddles were a brief ad hoc meeting or planning session that allows team members to voice positive feedback and any safety concerns. Daily huddles also ensure that the processes put in place are continued (Rakeover, 2018). Each morning at 10 a.m. and 10:30 a.m., a daily huddle was performed on the unit with the unit charge nurse, nurses, unit clerk, and the BRT team leader. The huddle reviewed all GH patients, positive feedback from the project, and safety concerns.

Measures

The team obtained a baseline of the staff's knowledge and attitude on reducing workplace violence at the start of the project. A content expert team consisted of nurse educators and Clinical Nursing Directors who were qualified individuals that have worked in the field and encountered these problems for years. They worked collaboratively to create the survey and the training based on the objectives of the class. The staff independently answered the survey before the training class. There was approximately 147 nursing staff on the two units, plus 20 security

personnel, and we obtained an 84% return response on the surveys. Demographics questions ask for gender, job title, and years of service. The same survey was re-administered to the staff at the end of the pilot.

The UHC SI was a reporting system for all adverse events at LAC-USC. Hospital-approved personnel such as the team's QI nurse have the authorization to extract the data from the SI system. The QI nurse obtained a baseline of assault incidents for the two pilot wards before starting the project and will abstract the number of assaults for the team each month. The team reviewed the monthly trend of assault incidents to evaluate the GH toolkit's effectiveness.

Evaluation

The re-implementation of the GH Tool Kit project started in September 2020, and commenced in March 2021. The project's assessment included 11 weeks of data from December 14, 2020, to February 27, 2021. The QI nurse utilized the collected data to evaluate the outcome and process measures (Table 4). The data from the SI report that reflected the number of assaults defined the interventions' effectiveness. The analysis of the staff pre and post-survey would determine the sustainability of the project. Positive feedback from the survey indicated that the staff believed in the process. Furthermore, when people believe in the process, they will utilize it on a routine basis, thus supporting the project's sustainability.

Table 4*Outcome and Process Measures*

Measure Type	Measure Definition	Measure Data Source
Outcome	Number of staff assaults	Monthly number of staff assaults from the SI system in the 2 med/surg units; data will be collected by the QI nurse weekly and recorded on a control chart. Assault data will also be used in a Time Between study to analyze the period from one assault to another.
Process	Number of BVC tools completed	Percentage of BVC tools completed daily; the number of tools completed/number of patients on the unit Data will be collected daily and recorded on a run chart.
Process	Number of GH signage outside room	The number of rooms with appropriate signage/The number of rooms needing signage. Data will be collected daily and recorded on a run chart.
Process	Number of BRT Security Rounds	The number of rounds completed/ The number of rounds required. Data will be collected daily and recorded on a control chart.
Process	Number of Huddles	The of huddles done/The number of required huddles. Data will be collected daily and recorded on a run chart.

Budget and Timeline

The budget for implementing the patient-to-staff assault reduction project included the cost of training instructors, training materials, nursing time to attend the training, materials needed for the project, and time required to collect and analyze the data (Table 5). The timeline below showed activities up to the dissemination (Table 6). After the defense, the project approval letter was submitted to the hospital's Chief Nursing Officer, and then IRB approval was requested. Due to the pandemic, IRB was not approved until December 11, 2020.

The GH project that was implemented in February 2020 was not fully adhered to due to the pandemic crisis that shifted the hospital's focus. The team prepared to re-implement the project in September 2020, and started data collection on December 14, 2020.

Table 5

Budget

Activity/Materials	Cost per unit	Estimated time/number	Total
Development of training program: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • PowerPoint presentation • Rights for the use of BVC • Training time (2 instructors) 	\$160/hr. n/a \$160/hr.	6 5	\$ 960 \$ 800
Scheduling of training time and registration during training (Clerical support used)	\$18/hr.	7	\$ 126
Printing materials for training	\$ 25	1	\$ 25
Materials for pilot wards: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 3" binders (1) • Golden Hand laminated postings • Printed BVC tool • Patient wrist bands 	\$ 5 \$ 20 \$ 25 \$ 60/box	2 2 2 2	\$10 \$ 40 \$ 50 \$ 120
Nursing time	\$ 60 (mean)	155 staff attending 1 hr. training class	\$ 9,300
Data Collection Time and Analysis (Registered Nurse)	\$ 60 (mean)	2/week x 12 (based on the 12-week pilot)	\$ 1,440
Total Cost			\$ 12, 871

Table 6*Timeline*

November-December 2019	January 2020	February 2020	March 2020	April 2020	May 2020
Meet with key stakeholders and identify pilot units	Literature review for proposal	Complete Table of Evidence	Complete Review of Literature		
Literature review on interventions	Plan implementation of interventions	Training classes	Request permission to use the IHI model	Complete CITI training	
Obtain approval to use BVC tool	Schedule Training classes	Meeting w/ head of Security and BRT team			
	Work on training materials	Disseminated supplies to pilot ward	COVID	COVID	COVID
June 2020	July 2020	August 2020	October 2020	November 2020	December 2020
Complete Methods and Evaluation	Meet with team to re-evaluate project	Submit IRB Administer survey	Re-administered survey	Refresher classes for GH Re-submit IRB	
Obtain adm permission to do project			Reinforce Training		Collect and analyze data
January 2021	February 2021	March 2021	April 2021		
Collect and analyze data	Collect and analyze data	Administer post-survey and analyze data	Dissemination		

Results

This section presents the data analysis results, including the quantitative survey results, the outcome measures, and the SI report on the number of patient-to-staff assaults. The patient-to-staff assaults for Ward A and B for 2019 were used as a baseline for the project. The project, first implemented in February 2020, was suspended due to the COVID-19 pandemic. By September 2020, as the pandemic crisis started to plateau, the project was restarted. The pre-survey was given to the staff and the security personnel on both wards. Staff was re-trained on the GH project and the use of the BVC tool. In December 2020, the project was IRB approved, and data collection started.

A sample of 141 employee surveys was received, of which 60 (84%) were from Ward A, 61 (78%) were from Ward B, and 20 (100%) were from the security team. The survey was administered during the first week of September 2020. The demographics of questionnaire respondents are summarized in Table 7. The respondents were 42.6% registered nurses, 3.5% licensed vocational nurses, 35.7% nursing attendants, 14.2% security personnel, and 6.4% clerical staff. The majority of the respondents were (65%) female. Furthermore, 50% of the staff had 1 to 5 years of service at the hospital. The post-survey was administered during the first week of March 2021. Demographics (Table 8) showed that a sample of 126 employee surveys was received, of which 53 (75%) were from Ward A, 61 (78%) were from Ward B, and 12 (60%) were from the security team. The demographics of pre and post-surveys were similar, with many female participants who had 1 to 5 years of service with the hospital.

Analysis of the pre- and post-survey (Figure 4) did not show a significant difference between the pre- and post-surveys; however, it did indicate that the staff favored the Golden Hand project. Using the Likert scale, respondents chose the following answers: (5) Strongly

agree, (4) Agree, (3) Neutral, (2) Disagree, and (1) Strongly disagree. The questions measured staff impressions of their ability to identify potentially assaultive/violent patients to help prevent staff assaults, the policies and procedures in place to prevent assault, the Golden Hand implementations, among other items (Table 8). The highest score was in response to staff's ability to identify potentially assaultive/violent patients to prevent staff assaults in their work area (Question 1, 4.35, and 4.29). The second highest score was if the GH implementation has made them more aware of the potentially assaultive patients on their unit (Question 5, 4.28). The lowest mean score was in response to the use of the patients' social and medical history to determine whether a patient has a potential for violence (Question 4, 3.87 and 3.95).

The survey question also measured how many times the staff has been assaulted in the last three months. Results were 177 (66%) said they have never been assaulted for the total pre- and post-surveys, 67 (25%) did not indicate, and the remaining stated one or more times.

Table 7

Characteristics of Pre-Questionnaire Respondents (n=141)

	n	%
Gender		
Male	42	29.8
Female	87	61.7
Undeclared	12	8.5
Job category		
Registered Nurse	60	42.6
Licensed Vocational Nurse	5	3.5
Nursing Attendant	46	32.6
Clerical Support	9	6.4
Security Personnel	20	14.2
Years of Service		
<1 year	6	4.3
1-5 years	73	51.8
6-10 years	10	7.0
11-15 years	21	14.9
16-20 years	6	4.3

21+ years	4	2.8
Undisclosed	21	14.9

Note: The pre-survey was administered in September 2020, for the re-implementation of the project.

Table 8

Characteristics of Post-Questionnaire Respondents (n=126)

	n	%
Gender		
Male	39	31.0
Female	82	65.0
Undeclared	5	4.0
Job category		
Registered Nurse	60	47.6
Licensed Vocational Nurse	4	3.2
Nursing Attendant	45	35.7
Clerical Support	5	4.0
Security Personnel	12	9.5
Years of Service		
<1 year	8	6.3
1-5 years	63	50.0
6-10 years	13	10.3
11-15 years	14	11.1
16-20 years	4	3.2
21+ years	5	4.0
Undisclosed	19	15.1

Note: The post-survey was administered in March 2021 after the project ended.

Figure 4*Pre- and Post-Survey*

Note: The seven questions pre- and post-surveys had the respondents specify their level of agreement to a five-point Likert Scale: 1) Strongly disagree; 2) Disagree; 3) Neutral; 4) Agree, and 5) Strongly agree.

Golden Hand Tool Kit

The GH Tool Kit contained using the BVC tool, GH signage, BRT participation, and safety huddle. Data were collected daily for the four measures from December 13, 2020, to February 27, 2021 (Table 11). Ward A utilized the BVC tool on every new admission and daily on all identified Golden Hand patients. Ward B, a medical-surgical behavioral ward, required a change process in December 2020, due to the higher assaults and patient population. They utilized the BVC tool on all their patients daily, and each shift on the patients identified as GH patients.

The security staff rounded on both wards frequently. Ward A data (Figure 5) showed security rounding an average of 3.3 times with a range of 0 to 8.8. Ward B, which tended to admit more medical-surgical patients with behavioral issues, had more security rounds done. Data for Ward B (Figure 6) indicated that security rounded 5.2 times with a range of 0 to 12. A c-chart was used to analyze this measure since the incidents are whole numbers independent of any other incident (Provost & Murray, 2011). Note that the special cause shown in December, 2020 for both wards was most likely the Hawthorne effect.

Figure 5

Security Rounds Ward A

Note: The security rounds are self-reported by the security staff and submitted to the security office.

Figure 6*Security Rounds Ward B*

Note: Security rounds are more frequent on Ward B since they are stationed on the ward as part of the BRT.

Patient-to-Staff Assault Incidents

Patient-to-staff assault incidents were extracted from the SI reporting system. Inclusion criteria were any type of patient-to-nurse assaults (verbal, physical, and threats) that occurred on Ward A and B. The assault data also captured staff injury caused by patients during restraint placements or activities of daily livings such as scratch, slap, spit, or kick. The number of patient-to-staff assaults on Ward A (Figure 7) from January 2019 to February 2020, was an average of 1.64 incidents with a range of 0-5.49. After the GH project, implementation data showed a significant improvement, with the average assault decreased to 0.58 with a range of 0-2.88. Time Between study (Figure 8) utilized a T chart to evaluate the length of time between

assault events. On Ward A, from January 2019, to February 2020; there was an average of 15.06 days between assaults with a range of 0-54.01 days. After the project implementation, the average number of days between assaults was 32.82 days, with a range of 0-150.62 days reflecting a significant improvement. Since the project re-implementation to date, there had been no assault incidents reported.

Figure 7

Patient-to-Staff Assaults Ward A

Note: Patient-to-staff assault data obtained from the SI reporting system. The GH Tool Kit continued to be used by the staff after the project was suspended.

Figure 8

Time Between Assaults Incidents on Ward A

Note: The graph shows the average number of days between assault events for GH implementation.

The c chart (Figure 9) shows the numbers of patient-to-staff assault incidents on Ward B. The graph showed the average assault incidents was 2.31 with a range of 0 - 6.86, with a special cause detected in December 2020. This significant spike triggered a change in the process on Ward B. Nurses were to assess all the patients daily using the BVC tool and then again each shift if the patient was identified as a GH. The Time Between study for Ward B (Figure 10) showed the average was 6.0 days between assaults with a range of 0 – 69.14 days with special cause detected from August to November 2019 of unidentifiable reason due to late analysis. After the project implementation, the time between assaults increased to 11.51 days with a range of 0 – 124 days. Another special cause was detected in November with a peak above the upper control

limit, followed by eight assaults in December. The project was re-implemented in December, and to date, there has been no assault incident reported.

Figure 9

Patient-to-Staff Assaults Ward B

Note: Patient-to-staff assault data obtained from the SI reporting system. The GH Tool Kit continued to be used by the staff after the project was suspended.

Figure 10

Time Between Assault Incidents on Ward B

Note: The graph shows the average number of days between assault events pre- and post-GH implementation.

Discussion

The patient-to-staff assault reduction using the GH Tool Kit was based on a prior successful implementation of a similar process in the emergency department and evidence support in the literature. The project started at the beginning of 2020 but was suspended shortly after due to the surge crisis, but the two MS wards continued to utilize the GH Tool Kit provided to them.

The project framework was based on the IHI Rapid Improvement Model. PDSA Cycle 1 was to train the staff, which was completed using the train-the-trainer model in February 2020. PDSA Cycle 2 was to implement the GH Tool Kit. In the study phase, all assaults were checked for accurate BVC scoring, Golden Hand signages posted appropriately, and patients had on their identifying wrist bands. A review of this process showed completion of BVC assessments, but we could not determine the score's accuracy from the observational assessments; the signage was posted, but the wristband was not placed because the patients were refusing or removing them. PDSA Cycle 3 was to implement BRT and Code Gold on Ward A and B. This cycle was completed, and the BRT team was made aware of GH patients on both wards during the safety huddle; however, we were unable to monitor the exchanged information during the huddles due to the short project time.

In September 2020, with plans to re-implement the project, a pre-survey was given to the staff. The pre-survey score actually reflected the processes that were put in place since February, 2020. This survey's mean score, n=126, was 4.06, which suggests that the staff agreed with the project and the intervention in place. When the COVID-19 crisis started to plateau, the QI team did more training on the GH project. The BVC assessment process was also changed on Ward B to capture the patient population's nonsensical behavior on that ward. Post-surveys were

collected in March, 2021, n=141 with a mean score of 4.15, which was slightly higher than the pre-survey. Overall, both the pre and post-survey supported the implementation of the GH Tool Kit.

The BVC was based on the exhibition of three patient characteristics (irritability, confusion, and boisterousness) accompanied by three behaviors (attack on objects, physical threats, and verbal threats) used to predict if the patient would be violent or aggressive within the next 24 hours (Moursel et al., 2018). Our project utilized the tool to assess the patient but only once upon admission and then every 24 hours if they were determined to be potentially violent or aggressive. If the patient scored a zero twice, having absence of the behaviors, they were no longer considered potentially violent. On Ward B, we noted that patients would score a zero on admission, but their characteristics and behavior would change during their stay in the hospital. Ward B implemented a process change on December 1, 2020, to assess the patients every day with a reassessment every shift for patients who scored one or higher with the BVC. Due to the unexpected delay of the start of the project that caused a constraint in data collection, we could not fully determine if this process had any valid effect on the assault rate.

Implications for Practice

The BVC tool is a validated tool utilized to predict violent behaviors; however, the nursing staff should never put their guards down when interacting with other patients who are not identified as GH. The GH Tool Kit is comprised of other valuable components such as huddles. However, it requires multidisciplinary participation and good communication to ensure that everyone is aware of the ward's safety concerns. Based on the staff surveys, the GH project appeared to have improved staff awareness and ability to handle violent patients. The project

should be continued on the medical-surgical wards, and the focus should be on the BVC tool to see if the identified patients caused the assaults.

Due to the continued rise in the number of patient-to-staff assaults, the employer has a responsibility to provide a safe working environment for their staff. The project team's commitment to decrease assaults in the MS wards has already improved staff morale and decreased sick calls related to WPV stress and injury.

Project Strengths and Limitations

The project was well structured with multidisciplinary staff involvement at all levels. Implementation was comprehensive and included education for the staff, an evidence-based violence predictor tool, BRT's involvement, and safety huddles. The main limitation was that the COVID-19 pandemic impacted the project's implementation by shifting the operational focus to the hospital's surge crisis. Although the project was suspended in March, 2020, the staff was permitted to use the training and tools provided. In December, after refresher training on the Golden Hand Tool Kit, the project was restarted. From December 18, 2020, to March 18, 2021, there have been no patient-to-staff assaults on Ward A or B.

Conclusion

Overall there is no substantial evidence that using a predictive tool can determine violent or aggressive behavior. However, there is some evidence to support that implementing the Golden Hand Tool Kit has improved the staff's sense of security and awareness of potentially violent patients. Data from the SI reports indicated no staff injury, suggesting that the severity of the assaults decreased, perhaps due to staff's increased awareness.

Workplace violence towards nurses is a severe problem and growing exponentially. Victims frequently experience physical, mental, and emotional repercussions that negatively impact their job performance and career progression. WPV interventions and change in processes are most likely to reverse the decreased job satisfaction, productivity, and increased turnover (Arnetz et al., 2019, Phillips, 2016). Expected outcomes from reliable and replicable processes will prepare staff to recognize and manage violent patients, resulting in a decreased number of patient-to-staff assaults and improving staff confidence in their employer and themselves to create and maintain a safe work environment.

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APPENDIX A

Project Approval from Chief Nursing Officer

Los Angeles County Board of Supervisors

Hilda L. Solis First District

Mark Ridley-Thomas Second District

Sheila Kuehl Third District

Janice Hahn Fourth District

Kathryn Barger Fifth District

Jorge Orozco Chief Executive Officer

Brad Spellberg, MD Chief Medical Officer

Edgar Solis, RN Chief Operating Officer

Annie Marquez, RN Interim Chief Nursing Officer

1200 N. State Street Inpatient Tower (IPT) 2nd Floor, Room C2K100 Los Angeles, CA 90033

Tel: (323) 409-2800 Fax: (323) 441-8030

To ensure access to high-quality, patient-centered, cost-effective health care to Los Angeles County residents through direct services at DHS facilities and through collaboration with community and university partners.

Health Services www.dhs.lacounty.gov

DATE: October 13, 2020

Department of Nursing LAC+USC Medical Center 1200 N. State Street Los Angeles, CA 90033

To the Institutional Review Boards of CSUF:

I am writing this letter at the request of Artiyanee Ann Boonjaluksa to confirm that we are working with her as she commences her quality improvement project, "Reducing Patient to Staff Assaults in the Medical Surgical Care."

I am aware that she will be conducting surveys with the staff, performing audits, and extracting number of fall incidences from the Safety Intelligence (SI) at LAC+USC Medical Center. Ms. Boonjaluksa will have approval to do such procedures for as long as she has IRB approval to do so.

I also confirm that employees, here at LAC+USC Medical Center, will participate in the recruitment or selection of participants. Staff in the Medical-Surgical Units will intervene with patients by performing interventions to decrease patient assault. Artiyanee Boonjaluksa and her quality improvement team will facilitate personnel who will conduct violence prediction screening.

If any unanticipated problems or adverse events are to occur, it is up to Artiyanee Boonjaluksa to report these events to the IRB at CSUF and the LAC+USC Chief Nursing Officer/designee as promptly as possible.

Artiyanee Boonjaluksa's quality improvement project will be a valuable contribution to the improvement of our hospital, and we will be happy to support this endeavor.

Sincerely,

[Redacted signature]

Annie Marquez, RN, MSN Interim Chief Nursing Officer

APPENDIX B

Permission to use IHI Model

WILEY

Book: The Improvement Guide: A Practical Approach to Enhancing Organizational Performance, 2nd Edition

Author: Gerald J. Langley, Lloyd P. Provost

Publisher: John Wiley and Sons

Date: Apr 1, 2009

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Order Completed

Thank you for your order.

This Agreement between Artiyanee A Boonjaluksa ("You") and John Wiley and Sons ("John Wiley and Sons") consists of your order details and the terms and conditions provided by John Wiley and Sons and Copyright Clearance Center.

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 Institution name California State University Fullerton
 Expected presentation date Aug 2021

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Mrs. Artiyanee Boonjaluksa

Order Details

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 Requestor type University/Academic
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 Portion Figure/table
 Number of figures/tables 4
 Will you be translating? No

Additional Data

Portions <http://www.ihl.org/resources/Pages/HowtoImprove/default.aspx>
 Attachment IHI Model.pdf

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APPENDIX C

Permission to use Broset Violence Predictor Tool

Re: Request Permission to Use BVC

Roger Almvik

4/19/2020 11:52 PM

To: Ann Boonjaluksa

Dear Ann, thanks for the interest in the BVC and of course you have my permission to use the tools as described. I believe you have already visited www.riskassessment.no (for free e-learning etc)? Please also visit the website of the Dutch IT company who holds the copyrights for all electronic use of the BVC (and hence the people you need to contact if you at any point want to BVC in to your medical record system); www.frenzs.org.

I am also glad to let you know that we are an international consortium/research group currently working on a scoping review on the use of BVC around the world and we hope to publish the review by the end of this year. So far we have identified nearly 100 publications from 44 countries, so this is really exiting 😊

Please let me know if you have further questions, need more info regarding the use of BVC etc, I am more than happy to of any help.

Best wishes

Roger

--

Dr. Roger Almvik
Senior Researcher, Dr.Philos, RN, RMN
St. Olavs University Hospital,Forensic Dept Brøset,
Centre for Research & Education in Forensic Psychiatry
Associate professor,NTNU, Dept. of Mental Health
PO 3250 Sluppen, N-7006 Trondheim, Norway
roger.almvik@ntnu.no, tel [+4745468880](tel:+4745468880)

APPENDIX D

Internal Review Board Approval

Date: 3-23-2021

IRB #: HSR-20-21-143

Title: Reducing Patient to Staff Assaults in the Medical-Surgical Care

Creation Date: 10-7-2020

End Date:

Status: **Approved**

Principal Investigator: Ann Boonjaluksa

Review Board: Exempt Board

Sponsor:

Study History

Submission Type Initial

Review Type Exempt

Decision **Exempt**

Key Study Contacts

Member Beverly Quaye

Role Co-Principal Investigator

Contact bquaye@fullerton.edu

Member Ann Boonjaluksa

Role Principal Investigator

Contact
artiyanee@csu.fullerton.edu

Member Ann Boonjaluksa

Role Primary Contact

Contact
artiyanee@csu.fullerton.edu

APPENDIX E

Brøset Violence Checklist

BROSET VIOLENCE CHECKLIST (BVC)

Ward: _____ Date: _____ Admission Date: _____ Time: _____

BEHAVIORS	SCORE 0-1
Confused	
Irritable	
Boisterous	
Physically Threatening	
Verbally Threatening	
Attacking Objects	
SUM	

Sum	Violence Risk	Actions
0	Small	None/Screen with BVC as Needed if Any Changes in Behavior Observed
1-2	Moderate	Activate Golden Hand*
3-6	High	Activate Golden Hand *

*If any of the behaviors include physical and verbal threats, consider activating a Code Gold

BEHAVIOR EXAMPLES

Confused - Appears obviously confused and disorientated. May be unaware of time, place or person. If well-known normal for patient, only an increase in behavior will result in an increase score by 1. e.g. If a well-known client normally is confused, this will give a score of "0."

• **Irritable** - Easily annoyed or angered. Unable to tolerate the presence of others.

• **Boisterous** - Behavior is overtly "loud" or noisy. For example slams doors, shouts out when talking etc.

• **Physically threatening** - Where there is a definite intent to physically threaten another person. For example: the taking of an aggressive stance; the grabbing of another person's clothing; the raising of an arm, leg, making of a fist or modelling of a head-butt directed at another.

Verbally threatening - A verbal outburst which is more than just a raised voice; and where there is a definite intent to intimidate or threaten another person. For example: verbal attacks, abuse, name calling, verbally neutral comments uttered in a snarling aggressive manner.

• **Attacking objects** - An attack directed at an object and not an individual. For example: the indiscriminate throwing of an object, banging or smashing windows; kicking, banging or head-butting an object; or the smashing of furniture.

Name/MRUN/DOB

Affix ORCHID Patient Label

APPENDIX F

Golden Hand Protocol

COUNTY OF LOS ANGELES DEPARTMENT OF HEALTH SERVICES
LAC+USC MEDICAL CENTER

GOLDEN HAND (AGITATED/VIOLENT PATIENT)

- PURPOSE:** The Golden Hand signage and wristband are used in areas as a communication tools to ensure all workforce members observe safety precautions when caring for an agitated/violent patient. The Golden Hand sign is placed outside the patient's room or in a visible location once they have been identified as being at an increased risk for agitated/violent behavior.
- ASSESSMENT:**
- Patient is assessed for the potential for violence upon admission, a minimum of every 24 hours and with change in condition using validated tool (Broset Violence checklist) (BVC)
 - A score greater than 2 indicates an increased potential for violent behavior and Golden Hand precautions should be observed.
- SAFETY:**
- Place the Golden Hand awareness sign outside the patient's room or in a visible location and apply appropriate wristband as applicable
 - Remove potentially harmful objects that could be used by the patient to harm self/others
 - Maintain close surveillance by assigning staff to be within sight and sound of patient at all times
 - Maintain a **MINIMUM** distance of a leg length from patient at all times, unless temporally necessary to administer physical care
 - Ensure 2 staff are present when administering physical care
 - Always maintain an escape route
 - Do not turn your back on the patient at any time
 - Request additional assistance if patient is violent toward self/others from:
 - Behavioral Response Team (Code Gold)
 - Unit/ward staff
 - Law enforcement
 - Remove source of agitation, if possible.
 - Utilize therapeutic communication techniques to facilitate problem solving:
 - Active listening
 - Reflection of feelings
 - Simple instructions/explanations
 - Reassurance that he/she is in a safe environment
 - Collaborate with other disciplines (e.g., provider, social worker, pharmacist, law enforcement/security) to clarify causes and develop strategies for behavior management.
 - Conduct huddles at shift change to share behavior management updates